

PROBLEMS OF SYNONYMY IN TERMINOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the role and function of synonyms in English terminology. The opinions of several scientists about synonyms have been analyzed. In particular, synonyms of economic terms are given as an example.

The phenomenon of synonymy, which is characteristic of other lexical units of the language, is also characteristic of terms. The problems of synonymy have been studied in linguistics, especially in terminology, for many years, but it is believed that they have not been solved yet. These problems include a number of issues such as the place of synonyms in various terminological systems, sources and ways of their appearance, classification of terminological synonyms and their development trends. The problem of synonymy in terminology has caused a heated debate among linguists. L.N. Rusinova explains that there is a phenomenon of synonymy in terminology, and emphasizes that the terms should be used in any communication between specialists in the field.¹

Thus, depending on the type of communication, the demand for terms varies. Sometimes it is necessary to use several terms to express one phenomenon. In modern linguistics, there are suggestions that terminology should be far from the phenomenon of synonymy. But the lack of synonymic phenomena in the terms weakens them functionally. . A number of linguists consider synonymy to be a positive phenomenon when studying terminology. They are: V.M. Leychik, V.A. Tatarinov, L.V. Alekseyeva, S.D. Shelov. but there are also linguists who do not agree with this opinion. Although linguists such as D.S. Lotte, V.P. Danilenko, A.A. Reformatsky, A.V. Lagutina recognize the existence of synonymy in terminology, they consider it unnecessary for terminology. A number of other linguists deny the existence of synonymy in terminology. They are: V.K. Favorin, A.B. Shapiro, E.N. Tolikina, V.N. Molodets, O.S. Akhmanova. Although linguists have different approaches to the phenomenon of synonymy in terminology, they have one common point. This idea is that terminology does not need synonymy, and that synonymy does no important work in terminology. They believe that the existence of a synonymous line in terminology complicates communication within the field.

¹ Rusinova L. N. О некоторых вопросах упорядочения и стандартизации терминологии(терминологическая синонимия) // Термины в языке и речи. Горький: Изд-во ГГУ, 1985. P-25-31

The main difference between synonyms in terminology and synonyms in other lexemes is that their semantic structure contains not only close and even identical meanings, but also different meanings that distinguish this term from other lexemes characterizing it. According to V. P. Danilenko, synonymy in terminology is one of the natural forms of manifestation of general language laws.² That is, their appearance is reasonable but unnecessary. It is common for any language to have many lexemes for expressing concepts. Natural selection takes place over time. That is, one of the synonymic series of these lexical units is given priority over the others.

It is known that the term is ambiguous in nature. Synonyms of the term also describe a certain event, object, or action, but emphasize slightly different details. The solution of synonymy problems helps to develop principles of organizing terminology. The theoretical importance of studying the phenomenon of synonymy in treasury terminology in English and Uzbek languages is characterized by the lack of research in this field of knowledge. In my opinion, it is correct to have synonyms in treasury terminology, but it should be different from synonyms in ordinary lexical units. That is, they do not describe the same concept in different ways, but now they illuminate the concept in different positions. In the field of treasury, there are many terms that are similar in meaning or express the same meaning,

For instance: **Asset**³-property, resources, possessions, holdings, effects, capital, valuables;

Revenue⁴ - income, proceeds, receipts, return, yield, interest, takings, net, profits;

Money⁵-currency, legal tender, medium of exchange, cash, specie, banknotes, change, lucre;

Allowance⁶- stipend, dole, pin, pocket money, quota, ration, pension, annuity, allocation;

Risk⁷- danger, peril, jeopardy, hazard, chance;

Price⁸- charge, cost, expense, outlay, amount, figure, worth, value, valuation;

Debt⁹ - due, obligation, indebtedness, liability, responsibility, accountability, encumbrance;

As we can see, although the treasury terminology is rich in synonyms, there are no two terms that describe exactly the same qualities of the concept. Each synonym revealed some aspect of the concept. There is one dominant word in the middle, and the rest of the synonyms are gathered around it. The advantages of having a series of synonyms in the field of treasury and finance - it serves to communicate in various activities of specialists in this field, to write articles and other scientific literature within the field. That is, depending on the goals of communication, the necessary synonym is chosen. From this point of view, expressing one concept using several different terms serves to clarify its meaning in a wider way. Synonymous diversity helps terminology to be lexically diverse. But on the other hand, the

² Danilenko V. P. Русская терминология: опыт лингвистического описания. М.: Наука, 1977. Page-246

³ Cambridge online dictionary

⁴ Cambridge online dictionary

⁵ Cambridge online dictionary

⁶ Cambridge online dictionary

⁷ Cambridge online dictionary

⁸ Cambridge online dictionary

⁹ Cambridge online dictionary

presence of several synonyms to express one concept can cause the difference between them to be known, even if it is imperceptible, which can lead to a violation of the meaning of the term. For this reason, the requirement of non-synonyms has been submitted to the standardized terminology.

References:

1. Rusinova L. N. О некоторых вопросах упорядочения и стандартизации терминологии(терминологическая синонимия) // Термины в языке и речи. Горький: Изд-во ГГУ, 1985
2. Danilenko V. P. Русская терминология: опыт лингвистического описания. М.: Наука, 1977
3. Maksym Vakulenko "TERM AND TERMINOLOGY: BASIC APPROACHES, DEFINITIONS, AND INVESTIGATION METHODS" Moskva IITF Journa 2013
4. Internet sources: Cambridge online dictionary